

Content Analysis of Job listings

Table 1

Table 1: Job listings with “data curator” in the title

Title	Count	Percentage
Data Curator	12	63.2%
Scientific Data Curator	2	10.5%
Research Data Curator	2	10.5%
Assistant Data Curator	1	5.3%
Humanities Data Curator	1	5.3%
GeoSpatial Data Curator	1	5.3%

Table 2

Table 2: Distribution of degree qualifications for data curators

Degree	Count	Percentage
MLIS	119	27.0%
PHD	34	7.7%
BA/BS	13	2.9%

Table 3

Table 3: Distribution of contributing countries by continent

Continent	Countries	Percentage
Europe	17	50.0%
Middle East	5	14.7%
Asia	4	11.8%
North America	3	8.8%
Oceania	2	5.9%
Africa	1	2.9%

Figure 1: Origin of job advertisements for data curator and non-data curator positions.

